

Analysis of knowledge and attitudes of pharmacy students towards the use of herbal medicines

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Abstract

The use of traditional remedies such as herbal medications has always been a part of cultural heritage and history in most parts of the Philippines. As pharmacists, it is our role to ensure that conventional treatments are neither contraindicated nor disadvantageous to various local herbal remedies. The aim of the study is to assess the attitude and extent of knowledge of St. Dominic College of Asia, BS Pharmacy students on herbal medicines. This study was employed using a structured online survey questionnaire given to thirty (30) pharmacy students enrolled in the College of Pharmacy, ten (10) per year level starting from second year until fourth year. A descriptive, cross sectional study methodology was conducted by distributing a pre-validated instrument to Bachelor of Science in Pharmacy students. A 15-item questionnaire was used to measure knowledge (1 = true and 2 = false) and 16-item questionnaire for determining the attitude (1 = strongly disagree to 5 = strongly agree) towards herbal medications. Of the thirty (30) surveys used, only twenty-seven percent (27%) believed their knowledge of herbal medications was insufficient to practice as a pharmacist. The average herbal medications knowledge score was (10.5±1.8). Students in the fourth (11.1±1.4) year had higher herbal knowledge scores compared to second year (9.8±1.2) and third year (10.6±2.1) students. However, the average attitude towards herbal medications was similar across all groups, second (3.6±0.4), third (3.7±0.4), and fourth year (3.7±0.4), respectively. As future pharmacists, pharmacy students must acknowledge the need to also learn about herbal supplements and other traditional medicines to be able to serve their patients well.

Keywords: Attitudes, BS pharmacy students, herbal medications, knowledge, St. Dominic College of Asia, traditional medicine.

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Introduction

Herbal medications have always been a part of the culture and tradition in the Philippines. Since antiquities, these types of remedies have always been sought out to cure different types of illnesses. In fact, some of these products have been studied and were made into a commercial drug. A significant increase was documented in the global consumption herbal medicines in the past three decades (Alsayari et al., 2018).

At present, herbal medications are still one of the popular products used by consumers (Sura et al., 2012). It is considered as a part of the Complementary and Alternative Medicine (CAM) therapy initiated by patients on themselves believing that these can cure their ailments (Harris et al., 2006; Tiralongo & Wallis, 2008). The belief that herbal medicines could promote healthier living is also one of the reasons why these products are in demand (Chang et al., 2007).

The problems with herbal medications, since they can be purchased from any store, oversight of healthcare professional is often neglected. Self-medication is a significant medication therapy problem since taking herbal supplements as treatment can be the cause masking of symptoms of the underlying disease as well as the interaction with primary therapy (Kostić et al., 2019). Thus, it is important that the roles of the pharmacists and physicians are emphasized in the proper usage of those products.

It is noteworthy that pharmacy schools will be responsible to prepare their students with enough knowledge to be able to do contemporary pharmacy practice. Since pharmacy students are future pharmacists who are the first point of contact to provide herbal medication information to patients, it is important to know their knowledge and attitude.

The objective of the present study was to assess and compare the knowledge and attitude of BS Pharmacy students from St. Dominic College of Asia, Bacoor, Philippines, towards herbal medications and to examine the factors that might be associated with attitude formation towards herbal medications.

Methodology

Study design and setting

A descriptive, cross sectional study methodology was conducted by sampling respondents from Bachelor of Science in Pharmacy Program at St. Dominic College of Asia, Bacoor, Cavite, who had completed at least one semester at the university. The study was conducted in May 2021. Data was collected from several pharmacy students currently enrolled in the present semester. Verbal and written consent was obtained from the participants and the nature and objectives of the research was discussed before administration of the survey questionnaires.

Study population

A total of thirty (30) respondents from the College of Pharmacy were enrolled in the study. A simple systematic sampling was used for the selection of study participants. The Pharmacy students interviewed was comprised of three groups: Year 2 (10 students), Year 3 (10 students) and Year 4 (10 students). For each year of study, participants were conveniently selected depending on their availability and desire to participate in the study.

Inclusion criteria

All second to fourth year students currently enrolled in BS Pharmacy undergraduate program at St. Dominic College of Asia, irrespective of age, gender, ethnicity, religion or social class. Only participants willing to take part in the study were enrolled.

Exclusion criteria

All first-year students in the BS Pharmacy program and other students taking different undergraduate programs were excluded from the study since they do not have yet a subject that tackles complementary and alternative medicine, including knowledge about herbal medicines during this year.

Data Collection

Data collection was done by using a validated structured questionnaire that was used in previous studies (Sura et al., 2012) with similar nature to the current study. The questionnaire was distributed through an online google forms survey to a total of 30 selected students and were asked to fill up the forms as honestly as possible. All forms were filled up and there were no incomplete forms that were noted. The questionnaire was designed to collect information on pharmacy students' knowledge and attitude towards herbal medications.

Section one includes demographic information such as the age and gender, other background data and assessment of past herbal use. Section two included fifteen herbal medication knowledge statements in a “true” or “false” choice format. Section three consisted of seventeen statements with a “Likert” scale from 1 (strongly disagree) through 5 (strongly agree).

Statistical analysis

Data was analyzed using Microsoft Office Excel version 2019 for the descriptive statistics, Pearson’s correlation, and Chi square analysis.

Results

Sample Characteristics

A total of 30 students successfully participated in the survey with 100% response rate for the second, third- and fourth-year BS Pharmacy students. The sample characteristics of second, third- and fourth-year students were summarized in Table 1. The mean (\pm SD) age of pharmacy students was 20.36 (\pm 1.36) years and approximately five-sixths were female.

Table 1. Sample characteristics by year enrolled

Characteristics	Frequency (%)			
	2nd year (N=10)	3rd year (N=10)	4th year (N=10)	Total (N=30)
Age (Mean \pm SD)	19.1 (\pm 0.9)	20.2 (\pm 0.4)	21.8 (\pm 1.4)	20.36 (\pm 1.3)
Gender				
Male	1 (10)	1 (10)	2 (20)	4 (13.3)
Female	9 (90)	9 (90)	8 (80)	26 (86.6)
Have you received or completed any courses that provided information on herbal medications?				
Yes	8 (80)	10 (10)	8 (80)	26 (86.6)
No	2 (20)	0 (0)	2 (20)	4 (13.3)
Based on courses you have taken; do you have adequate knowledge about herbal medications to practice as a pharmacist?				
Yes	7 (70)	8 (80)	7 (70)	22 (73.3)
No	3 (30)	2 (20)	3 (30)	8 (26.6)
Do you need more information regarding herbal medications?				
Yes	10 (10)	10 (10)	10 (10)	30 (100)
No	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)
Where do you feel you received the majority of your herbal medications’ information? (Check all that applies)				
Pharmacy courses	9 (90)	9 (90)	10 (100)	28 (93.3)
Books	3 (30)	7 (70)	7 (70)	17 (56.6)
Internet	8 (80)	10 (100)	7 (70)	25 (83.3)
Journals	4 (40)	9 (90)	6 (60)	19 (63.3)
Others	3 (30)	1 (1)	0 (0)	4 (13.3)

Students’ knowledge regarding Herbal Medication

The assessment of student knowledge contains statements comprising the herbal medications knowledge test along with the number of correct responses and percentage were summarized in Table 2. The mean (\pm SD) knowledge score across all groups was 10.5 \pm 1.8 (maximum 15). Fourth year students (11.1 \pm 1.4) had slightly better knowledge scores compared to second year (9.8 \pm 1.2) and third year (10.6 \pm 2.1) students.

Table 2. Students' responses to herbal medications knowledge questions

Knowledge Statements	Response	Correct Responses (%)			
		2nd year (N=10)	3rd year (N=10)	4th year (N=10)	Total (N=30)
St. John's Wort is most commonly used for depression.	True	8 (80)	8 (80)	9 (90)	25 (83.3)
Ginseng may cause an increased risk of bleeding.	True	2 (20)	7 (70)	6 (60)	15 (50)
Grapefruit Juice is metabolized through the CYP450 system.	True	8 (80)	8 (80)	6 (60)	22 (73.3)
Saw Palmetto is commonly used for treatment of headache.	False	8 (80)	6 (60)	8 (80)	22 (73.3)
Fish oil can help decrease the risk of heart attack and stroke.	True	10 (100)	10 (100)	9 (90)	29 (96.7)
Ginseng should be used in caution in patients with renal dysfunction.	True	8 (80)	8 (80)	7 (70)	23 (76.7)
Cranberry juice has been shown to be effective in treating urinary tract infections.	False	1 (10)	2 (20)	0 (0)	3 (10)
Kava is most commonly used for anxiety.	True	9 (90)	9 (90)	6 (60)	24 (80)
St. John's Wort is contraindicated in pregnancy.	True	5 (50)	10 (100)	7 (70)	22 (73.3)
An adverse drug effect of St. John's Wort is photodermatitis.	True	5 (50)	5 (50)	7 (70)	17 (56.7)
Feverfew is safe for use in pregnant women.	False	6 (60)	7 (70)	9 (90)	22 (73.3)
Prolonged use of kava can cause skin discoloration.	True	8 (80)	8 (80)	8 (80)	24 (80)
An adverse effect of saw palmetto is hair loss.	False	5 (50)	3 (30)	9 (90)	17 (56.7)
Echinacea is commonly used for the treatment of cold and flu symptoms.	True	7 (70)	6 (60)	10 (100)	23 (76.7)
Glucosamine plus chondroitin may reduce knee pain or slow the progression of Osteoarthritis.	True	8 (80)	9 (90)	10 (100)	27 (90)

Students' Attitude towards Herbal Medications

Table 3 contains the mean scores and standard deviations for attitudinal questions overall and by class. The overall mean attitude score was between neutral and agree (3.7 ± 0.4). The average attitude towards herbal medications was similar across all three (3) years; 3.6 ± 0.4 (second year), 3.7 ± 0.4 (third year) and 3.7 ± 0.4 (fourth year) respectively ($p = 0.25$). Students reported positive attitude towards herbal medications for personal and family use (Table 3). They indicated a favorable attitude towards efficacy of herbal medications. However, they agreed with statements that herbal medications are a form of quackery, gives negative influence on pharmacies and a threat to public health.

Table 3. Students' attitude towards herbal medications

Characteristics	Mean±SD			
	2nd year (N=10)	3rd year (N=10)	4th year (N=10)	Total (N=30)
I have used herbal medications for self-treatment before.	2.7±1.2	3.9±1.1	3.5±1.2	3.4±1.2
Someone in my immediate family has used herbal medicines frequently in the past.	4.0±1.3	4.3±0.8	3.7±0.8	4.0±1.0
Herbal medications are efficacious.	3.7±0.5	4.2±0.6	3.4±0.8	3.8±0.7
As a consumer, I have actively sought information regarding herbal medicines.	3.4±0.7	4.0±0.9	3.4±0.8	3.6±0.9
Herbal medications are threat to public health	2.7±0.6	2.5±1.1	2.7±0.6	2.6±0.8
Herbal medications can be safely used with a prescription medication.	3.7±0.8	3.6±0.8	3.4±0.9	3.6±0.9
Most herbal medications have a high degree of placebo effect.	3.3±0.5	3.6±0.8	3.6±1.2	3.5±0.9
Herbal medications are a good economical alternative to conventional medicines for patients who self-select.	3.8±0.8	3.8±0.6	3.2±1.1	3.6±0.9
The quality of herbal medications is well-accepted by FDA.	4.2±0.4	4.1±0.7	3.6±0.7	4.0±0.7
Herbal medications are well accepted by the National Association of Boards of Pharmacy.	3.7±0.5	3.8±0.6	3.9±0.6	3.8±0.6
The doses of commercially marketed herbal medications have been well standardized.	3.5±1.0	3.7±0.8	3.8±0.6	3.7±0.8
Herbal medications are only a form of quackery.	2.6±0.8	2.3±1.3	2.9±0.7	2.6±1.0
Herbal medications should be sold only in a pharmacy.	3.7±0.7	4.0±0.9	4.3±0.8	4.0±0.8
Carrying herbal medications may have a negative influence on a pharmacy's image.	2.6±0.8	2.2±1.4	3.0±0.8	2.6±1.1
The profit potential is high with herbal medications.	3.2±0.4	3.4±0.8	3.6±0.7	3.4±0.7
Carrying herbal medications may increase my liability.	3.2±0.4	2.8±1.0	3.3±0.5	3.1±0.7

Discussion

Findings of this study showed that overall herbal medications knowledge score of pharmacy students was 10.5 out of 15 and perceived that they had adequate knowledge about herbal medications. Overall, pharmacy students had between neutral to agreeing attitude towards herbal medications. The study also demonstrated that fourth year pharmacy students had higher knowledge compared to second- and third-year students which could be due to herbal medication information provided to them through different advanced pharmacy subjects.

Use of herbal medications in the Philippines has already been long practiced since the ancient times and pharmacist needs to give more information to the patient pertaining to herbal medications indications, contraindications, doses, and herb-drug interactions. Therefore, it is important for pharmacists to have sufficient knowledge about herbal medications to counsel patients (Marrone, 1999; Welna & Hassall, 2003).

Thus, it is increasingly important that pharmacists receive prior education regarding herbal medications. Herbal medication information has been incorporated into curriculum in many pharmacy schools mostly through advance pharmacy subjects such as drug discovery and development, pharmacology, clinical pharmacy, and therapeutics (Evans & Evans, 2006).

Fourth year students had higher knowledge compared to second year students. This could be explained due to their exposure to herbal medication information in their advanced subjects. Whereas, second year students had not received any formal herbal medication knowledge yet through pharmacy coursework and third year students received only minimal information about herbal medication and their effects. Therefore, providing herbal medication knowledge might increase student's knowledge which could be helpful to practice as a pharmacist (Rickert et al., 1999).

Limitations

The study has several limitations which includes the factors that affects student responses which cannot be studied over time. Also, the knowledge as well as attitudes of students regarding herbal medications may change overtime, therefore, a longitudinal study may be performed to explain further these behaviors. The findings on this study are based on the student views and the result of this survey only represents the opinion of students enrolled in BS Pharmacy program of St. Dominic College of Asia, which cannot be generalized to other universities across the country.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the study indicated that pharmacy students had adequate knowledge about herbal medications to apply to practice but still needs and is willing to learn more about herbal medicines. Moreover, the attitude towards herbal medications was between neutral to increase in agreements with the statements, which may be attributed with increased in knowledge.

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